

methanol (25 ml) and refluxed for 4 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol (88%), m.p. 185° (Found: C, 69.50; H, 4.75; N, 18.90). $C_{13}H_{11}N_3O$ requires C, 69.33; H, 4.88; N, 18.67%. Similarly, 4-substituted benzalisoniazides were prepared (Table 1).

2-Phenyl-3-(p-pyridylcarbonyl)-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones: 4-Benzalisoniazide (0.01 mol) was condensed with thiomalic acid (0.01 mol) in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride (0.5 g) at 160° for 2 h. The temperature was then raised to 180° for 30 min°. The product was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution and reprecipitated with hydrochloric acid and crystallised from ethanol (52%), m.p. 150° (Found: C, 57.20; H, 4.45; N, 11.90). $C_{17}H_{16}N_3O_4S$ requires C, 57.14; H, 4.20; N, 11.76%. Similarly, 4-substituted benzalisoniazides were treated with thiomalic acid (Table 2).

Antimicrobial screening: The purified products were screened for antimicrobial activity by cup-plate¹⁰ method using a species of gram-positive bacteria, i.e. *S. aureus* and *B. megaterium* and a species of gram-negative bacteria, i.e. *E. coli*. The testing was carried out in DMF solution at a concentration of 10 mg ml⁻¹. The zones of inhibition of the test solution (0.5 mg) were recorded.

The condensation products with thiomalic acid are more active as compared to that of 4-substituted benzalisoniazide. Bromophenol residue enhances the activity against *B. megaterium* and *E. coli*.

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Amidomethylation of 5/6-Nitrobenzimidazole. Synthesis and Biological Activities of Certain 1-(N-Alkyl/Arylamidomethyl)-6-nitrobenzimidazoles†

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THE syntheses of several types of amidomethyl compounds including their varied biological and pharmacological activities have been reported in recent years¹⁻⁵. It has also been a fact that the benzimidazole moiety itself is a formidable pharmacophore and it is still more so with a nitro substituent at 5/6-position⁶. Therefore, in continuation of our studies on aminomethylation and amidomethylations of benzimidazoles⁷⁻⁹, it was desirable to conduct amidomethylations on 5/6-nitrobenzimidazole and to determine the structure, orientation and pharmacological efficacy of the products.

Scheme 1

5/6-Nitrobenzimidazole (2, Scheme 1) has been synthesised for the purpose from 4-nitro-*o*-phenylenediamine (1) by a standard method¹⁰. Compound 2 has been condensed with paraformaldehyde and various carboxamides (3) separately in ethanol adopting a modified Einhorn-Tsherniac procedure to get a single product in each case. The compounds have been purified by column chromatography using alumina (neutral) as an adsorbent and characterised by their analytical and spectral data (Table 1) as 1-(*N*-alkyl/arylamidomethyl)-5/6-nitrobenzimidazoles (4/5), in view of the possible tautomerism of compound 2.

It has been suggested that benzimidazole (2) reacts first with formaldehyde to give the benzimidazole-1-methylol which subsequently loses a water

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL, ANALYTICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF 1-(N-ALKYL/ARYLAMIDOMETHYL)-6-NITROBENZIMIDAZOLES* (5)

Compd. no.	NH-COR	Molecular formula	M.p. °C	Nitrogen % : Found/(Calcd.)	Eluent	δ (ppm)
1.	Chloroacetamido	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	182	20.78 (20.85)	CHCl ₃ -EtOAc (1:1)	—
2.	Benzamido	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂	205	18.89 (18.92)	CHCl ₃	4.92 (2H, d, N-CH ₂ -N), 9.21 (1H, b, CO-NH) 7.02-7.56 (8H, m, Ar-H)
3.	Phenylacetamido	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂	238	18.14 (18.06)	CHCl ₃ -EtOAc (2:1)	4.98 (2H, d, N-CH ₂ -N), 8.42 (2H, s, CH ₂ -CO), 9.30 (1H, b, CO-NH), 7.12-7.56 (9H, m, Ar-H)
4.	Phenoxyacetamido	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₃	164	17.09 (17.17)	CHCl ₃	4.89 (2H, d, N-CH ₂ -N), 4.94 (2H, s, CO-CH ₂ -O), 7.94-7.81 (9H, m, Ar-H), 9.18 (1H, b, CO-NH)
5.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenylamido	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	196	17.01 (16.99)	CHCl ₃ -EtOAc (1:2)	4.92 (2H, d, N-CH ₂ -N), 7.48-7.96 (8H, m, Ar-H), 9.20 (1H, b, CO-NH)
6.	<i>p</i> -Anisamido	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₃	258	17.12 (17.17)	CHCl ₃ -EtOAc (1:1)	—
7.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenoxyacetamido	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₃ Cl	251	15.59 (15.53)	CHCl ₃ -EtOAc (1:2)	—
8.	Salicylamido	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₃	246	17.88 (17.95)	CHCl ₃	—
9.	Succinimido	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₃	220	20.50 (20.48)	C ₆ H ₆ -CHCl ₃ (1:2)	—
10.	Phthalimido	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₃	260	17.48 (17.39)	CHCl ₃	—

* Yield 70-90%, $\nu_{\max}$ (nujol) 3400-3390 (CO-NH), 1710-1650 (NH-COR), 1565-1560 and 1345-1340 cm⁻¹ (Ar-NO₂).

TABLE 2—BIOLOGICAL AND PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF 1-(N-ALKYL/ARYLAMIDOMETHYL)-6-NITROBENZIMIDAZOLES (5)

Compd. no.	Antibacterial ^a		Antifungal ^b		Analgesic activity ^c			Antiinflammatory ^c
	<i>P. ovalis</i>	<i>B. megaterium</i>	<i>C. lunata</i>	<i>D. rostrata</i>	Tail-clip	Hot-plate	Writhing	Rat-paw oedema method
1.	8	10	52.07	43.40	32	28	28	30
2.	5	8	48.68	42.00	—	—	—	30
3.	—	—	69.02	70.11	48	45	46	50
4.	4	—	65.37	66.42	62	65	60	65
5.	10	12	100.00	100.00	—	—	—	35
6.	7	10	80.15	62.66	45	45	40	38
7.	16	12	75.45	68.88	—	—	—	28
8.	15	14	70.98	69.27	50	52	50	55
9.	6	8	30.66	28.84	—	—	—	42
10.	12	10	52.78	50.14	—	—	—	38
Bavistin	—	—	8.00	9.26	—	—	—	—
Aspirin	—	—	—	—	68	65	60	62
Phenylbutazone	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	48

^a Zone of inhibition in mm at 100 μ g ml⁻¹ concentration.

^b % germination inhibition at 250 μ g ml⁻¹ concentration.

^c % protection at dose of 100 mg/kg of body weight.

molecule in the presence of acid (HCl) to form 1,5- or 1,6-benzimidazolemethylene cations. The relative higher stability of 1,6-benzimidazolemethylene cation through its resonance may be considered as the proof for the preferential formation of 1-(N-alkyl/arylamidomethyl)-6-nitrobenzimidazoles (5). This observation is in agreement with the earlier findings.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord-232 spectrophotometer in nujol mull and pmr spectra on a Varian SM-360 (90-MHz) spectrophotometer using TMS as an internal standard.

1-(N-Alkyl/Arylamidomethyl)-6-nitrobenzimidazoles (5). General procedure: 5/6-Nitrobenzimidazole

(2; 0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed with paraformaldehyde (0.01 mol) and the appropriate carboxamide (3; 0.01 mol) in the presence of a trace of concentrated hydrochloric acid, on a water-bath for 3 h. Ethanol was removed by distillation as far as possible and the residue was chilled overnight in a refrigerator. The crystalline product thus resulted was filtered, washed with a minimum quantity of ethanol and dried. It was purified over a column of alumina (neutral) using suitable eluents to get pure 1-(N-alkyl/arylamidomethyl)-6-nitrobenzimidazole (5).

Biological activities:

Acute toxicity: For the toxicity studies of the present compounds albino mice of either sex weighing about 20 g were taken in groups of five each. They were deprived of food for 16 h and then

administered graded doses of the test compound in the form of gum acacia suspension, intraperitoneally. The mortality of mice in each group was recorded during the next 24 h for the purpose of calculating LD₅₀ value.

Antimicrobial activity: The antibacterial activity of the compounds was assayed against two bacteria, *Pseudomonas ovalis* and *Bacillus megaterium*, at 100 µg ml⁻¹ concentration by the filter paper disc method¹¹. They were also screened for their antifungal activity by a standard method¹² against two phytopathogenic fungi, *Curvularia lunata* and *Dreschlera rostrata* at a concentration of 250 µg ml⁻¹. Bavistin, a commercial fungicide was employed as a standard.

Analgesic and antiinflammatory activities: The analgesic and antiinflammatory activities of the compounds were determined by standard methods¹³⁻¹⁵ at a dose of 100 mg/kg body weight using albino mice and rats, respectively. Aspirin and phenylbutazone were employed as standards.

The results of all these investigations are presented in Table 2.

It was encouraging to note that all the ten compounds were non-toxic even at a dose of 1200 mg/kg body weight. Perusal of Table 2 reveals that compound 7 was more effective against both the bacteria, followed by compound 8. Compounds 10, 5, 6 and 1 were found to be moderate bactericides. Compound 5 was proved to be a potential fungicide as it could cause total inhibition of both the fungi, followed by compounds 6 and 7. All the compounds were shown to be superior over the commercial fungicide, Bavistin.

Compound 4 with phenylacetamido moiety exhibited a notable analgesic and antiinflammatory activities and almost it excelled aspirin. A moderate analgesic activity of compounds 8, 3, 6 and 1 was also recorded. All the compounds exhibited reasonable antiinflammatory activity which was superior over that of phenylbutazone.

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Synthesis of 2-Aminonicotinaldehyde Hydrazones as Possible Antimicrobial Agents

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A good deal of importance is being given to hydrazones due to their wide use as antibacterial¹⁻³, antifungal⁴, insecticidal^{5,6}, hypoglycemic⁷, amoebicidal⁸ and antiinflammatory⁹ agents. Some of the hydrazones have also been found to possess antitubercular¹⁰ property. Isonicotinic acid hydrazide is found superior to some other pyridine and non-pyridine hydrazides towards tuberculostatic activity¹¹. With a view to reduce toxicity due to free amino group, the condensation products of a number of hydrazides with various aldehydes and ketones were also examined¹². Taking into account the varied activities exhibited by hydrazones, a series of hitherto unknown hydrazones derived from 2-aminonicotinaldehyde have been made in the present investigation.

The compounds described in this communication have been synthesised by the condensation of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde with different aliphatic, aromatic and heteroaromatic acid hydrazides in ethanol in the presence of a trace of glacial acetic acid. Relatively higher yields were obtained when the reaction was conducted in dry benzene and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid. The purity and homogeneity of all the compounds were tested by tlc and elemental analysis.

The structures of these compounds have been established by a combination of elemental analyses (Table 1) and spectral (ir, mass and pmr) data. The ir spectra of these hydrazones showed the characteristic bands at 3400, 3250 (NH₂), 3150 (NH), 1660 (amide carbonyl), 1600 (C=C or C=N), 1570, 1460, 1380, 1240, 1080, 980 and 900 cm⁻¹. The